

Feature article

Analysis of the Capabilities of Embedded Systems in Intra Prediction Video Coding

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Abstract - With the increased use of mobile devices, and embedded systems, battery life has become of vital importance. Thus, in the video coding field, energy consumption has joined compression efficiency and computational complexity as a key parameter. Energy consumption is one of the most important factors to consider in any video-intensive application due to its relationship to the autonomy of these devices. This paper aims to carry out a performance and temperature analysis of two embedded systems (Raspberry Pi 4 and Jetson Nano), which are used in multiple applications and fields, including video encoding, and a consumption study of different encoders of various video standards executed on them. The analysis will consider parameters such as the compression rate, the video quality using an objective metric (PSNR), and the computing time over an intra scenario. In this study, three software encoders and three hardware encoders implementing different video standards have been analyzed: x264 (H.264/AVC), x265 (HEVC), rav1e (AV1), omxh264enc (H.264/AVC), nvv4l2h264enc (H.264/AVC) and nvv4l2h265enc (HEVC). Finally, the results demonstrate that real-time video streaming using hardware encoders is only achievable for the Full-HD resolution format.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, video encoding systems, or encoders, play a critical role, especially when it comes to real-time video streaming. A vast number of people currently broadcast news in the form of video, and the speed at which they report events can shape the world [1].

The goal of encoders is to reduce the video bitrate, reducing the size of the video stream while maintaining the visual quality. For this purpose, they endeavor to eliminate the redundancies present in the video. Furthermore, in the case of real-time video encoding, time spent on encoding is a critical factor. Encoding is also necessary to store and distribute media content, especially

high-resolution formats (HD, 4K, and 8K), due to their large video sequence size.

The new embedded systems include specific video encoding hardware, but they can also run on CPUs most of the video encoding standards. Thus, the power consumption factor of these devices becomes particularly relevant in embedded systems that are powered by batteries. There are several embedded systems on the market that are capable of supporting video encoding, and they differ in terms of quality, compression efficiency, and computing time.

The main goal of this paper is to perform an analysis that includes both the consumption and encoding performance of different encoders and video standards on two embedded systems,

namely Raspberry Pi 4, developed by the Raspberry Pi Foundation, and Jetson Nano, developed by Nvidia. The two embedded systems have great market penetration and are commonly used in a variety of tasks, including video encoding. Currently Raspberry Pi 4 is the most widely sold and used embedded system in the world [2]. Meanwhile, Jetson Nano is a high-performance and low-cost embedded system whose hardware characteristics, which are detailed in section IV.B, provide great computing power (higher than Raspberry Pi 4) [3] [4].

The idea is to analyze and study which encoder offers the best performance in terms of bitrate, quality, computing time, and power consumption under certain operating conditions. These conditions may vary over time due to the increase in temperature of the embedded system in question.

During the encoding process, only the intra prediction scheme will be used. In applications which we need stored high quality video in the embedded system, such as photography storage, professional edition and postproduction, the intra prediction encoding is recommended, instead of inter prediction encoding using motion estimation tools, in order to reduce compression complexity and minimization of the impact of errors. We want high quality sequences, so we use intra frames which are ones with the best quality and the ones that most minimize the impact of errors. In addition, Nvidia recommends decoding in training of video neural networks with only intra frames, so an intra encoding could be used in this type of applications [5]. Also, the Secure Digital (SD) cards used in the embedded system are key, as it requires a large storage space and a write rate that supports the wide band of video encoding. Fortunately, on the market there are SD cards with these characteristics.

On each embedded system, specific encoders will be run, some of them using the system's hardware implementation to improve the performance compared with software encoding. The study of several parameters is carried out to analyze the encoders' performance and the benefits offered by each embedded system. On the one hand, in order to analyze an encoder's performance, it is essential to study its rate-distortion, and the computational cost is a factor to consider for real-time video encoding. On the other hand, to study the encoders' energy consumption on each embedded system, we have chosen to use joules per frame as the measurement unit [6], and the temperature curve over the full

encoding time. In addition, the temperature measurement in degrees Celsius was selected.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the video encoding standards and encoders to be analyzed. Section III describes the intra coding scheme and its implementation in the different video standards that will be studied and analyzed. Section IV details the hardware of the two embedded systems used and the energy consumption and temperature measurement processes applied. Then, the results of the study and their analysis are presented in section V. Finally, Section VI is devoted to the conclusions of the paper and lines for future work.

II. STANDARDS AND VIDEO ENCODERS

A video compression standard only defines the process to be carried out to decode an encoded bitstream, imposing additional restrictions on how the output bitstream must be structured, that is, how the decoder must interpret the syntax. In this way, encoders can be developed and implemented entirely free. The only condition is that the generated bitstream can be decoded by a decoder that follows the rules of a specific standard [7].

Thus, there may be several encoder implementations of the same video standard, differing from each other, for example, in the directional prediction modes used or in the mechanisms by which the block is split or encoded. To compare all encoders fairly, the encoders were set to not skip intra prediction modes. For the study and analysis in this paper, three different implementations of video encoder standards have been used: Advanced Video Coding (AVC), High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC), and AOMedia Video one (AV1).

A. Advanced Video Coding

H.264/AVC [7] is a video standard that was approved in 2003 by the working group called Joint Video Team (JVT). This standard was officially named H.264/AVC by ITU-R [8], and MPEG-4 Part 10 by ISO / IEC.

Many encoders have been implemented following this standard, with x264 being the most popular one and used by products and services such as YouTube, Facebook, and VLC Player. Furthermore, it can be configured to directly encode sequences with the intra prediction scheme, and it is integrated into the FFmpeg software. In view of all this, x264 was chosen to study both embedded systems.

Regarding hardware encoding, two different implementations of the H.264/AVC standard have been used, one for each embedded system. These hardware implementations can be called through a framework known as GStreamer. This framework features a hardware-based encoder known as omxh264enc [9]; this encoder works in the Raspberry Pi. In the case of Jetson Nano, the framework is integrated with the second version of Video4Linux (V4L2), which is a collection of device drivers and an application programming interface (API) for supporting real-time video capture on Linux systems that include the H.264/AVC hardware encoder called nvv4l2h264enc [9].

B. High Efficiency Video Coding

HEVC is an evolution of the H.264/AVC standard and was approved in January 2013 by the *Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding* (JCT-VC). This standard was officially named H.265 by ITU-R [10], and MPEG-H Part 2 by ISO/IEC [11].

Many software and hardware encoders have been developed following the guidelines of this standard. Hardware implementations are faster at encoding sequences, while software encoders have better quality and bitstream characteristics. For the analysis and study carried out in this paper, we initially considered using a x265 software encoder, and another hardware encoder, namely Nvidia Encoder (NVENC).

The x265 encoder is available as an open-source software library under the GNU General Public License (GPL) (recursive acronym for "GNU's Not Unix"). It is written in C++ and assembly language for x86-64, ARM-V6, ARM-V7, and PowerPC architecture processors. It is multiplatform and integrated into FFmpeg. Like x264, it allows you to encode sequences in intra mode with a single command, and it can be run on Jetson Nano.

With regards to NVENC, it is a hardware implementation of HEVC developed by the multinational Nvidia. It has been available for use on Nvidia graphics cards since the Kepler generation and can encode sequences up to 8K

resolution, depending on the graphics card used. Contrary to expectations, it is not compatible with the Jetson Nano [12], and that remains the case today. Obviously, it is not possible to run it on Raspberry Pi 4. Therefore, it was not considered in the study.

As in the case of the HEVC standard, the GStreamer framework has been used alongside V4L2, which allows calls, from an API, to the nvv4l2h265enc hardware encoder [9].

C. AOMedia Video 1

In contrast to AVC and HEVC, AV1 is a royalty-free, non-standard, and open-source video compression format mainly designed for streaming services. It was initially released in March 2018, and the latest version dates from January 2019. That implies that it is the most recent video compression format of those discussed in this paper. It has been developed by the Alliance for Open Media (AOMedia) consortium, which was founded in 2015 and brings together companies that provide video on demand, such as Netflix and Amazon, web browsers, such as Mozilla, content producers, and other top-technology companies such as Intel and Nvidia. AV1 is considered as the successor to the VP9 compression format [13].

At the moment, there are not many encoders of this standard due to its recent development. Two of the available encoders are Scalable Video Technology for AV1 (SVT-AV1) and rav1e. For our assessments, rav1e was chosen since SVT-AV1 can only be run on systems with a fifth-generation Intel processor onwards. However, rav1e supports the embedded systems under study.

As of the date of publication of this paper, the rav1e encoder is still under development, so the version used (version 0.1.1) is not the final one. It is cross-platform software and released under the Berkeley Software Distribution (BSD 2) license. Finally, rav1e can run on both Raspberry Pi 4 and Jetson Nano, so it has been chosen for our study.

Table 1 shows all the encoders used in this paper, classified by type (hardware or software) and the embedded system on which they run.

Table 1. Encoders used in this paper, classified by type and embedded system.

	Rapsberry Pi 4		Jetson Nano	
	Hardware	Software	Hardware	Software
H.264/AVC	omxh264enc	x264	nvv4l2h264enc	x264
HEVC	-	-	nvv4l2h265enc	x265
AV1	-	rav1e	-	rav1e

III. INTRA PREDICTION

Intra prediction is characterized by constructing the prediction samples using information present in the image itself, unlike inter prediction, which uses information from other images in the sequence. In this way, the temporal dependence on the rest of the images that make up the sequence is eliminated, something that cannot occur in inter prediction. In other words, only the spatial redundancy of the image in question is specifically exploited. Below, the characteristics of this type of prediction are analyzed for the video compression standards listed in the previous section.

In the H.264/AVC standard, the image is divided into 16x16 pixel MacroBlocks (MBs) to carry out intra prediction. There are three possible partitions of the MB in luminance, whose sizes are: 16x16, 8x8, and 4x4 pixels. Depending on the size of the block, different prediction modes have been defined [7]:

- 16x16 (luma): a single 16×16 prediction block is generated using 4 possible prediction modes: vertical, horizontal, DC, and plane.
- 8x8 (luma) and 4x4 (luma): 9 prediction modes have been defined, including 8 directional and 1 non-directional mode (DC).

On the other hand, in the case of chrominance, a prediction block is generated for each chrominance component, using the same prediction mode for both chrominance components, Cb and Cr. There are 4 possible prediction modes available for both chrominances: DC, horizontal, vertical, and plane.

When applying these directional modes, the high spatial correlation between a block and its neighboring pixels belonging to the upper, upper-left, upper-right, and left blocks is exploited. Once the block size has been determined using a cost function, the encoder chooses the optimal prediction mode to use.

The difference between choosing a small prediction block (4x4 pixels) or a large prediction block (16x16 pixels) is that the small one usually provides a more accurate prediction and, therefore, a smaller residual. The disadvantages are that the encoding time is longer, and more bits are required to encode the prediction mode since there are more blocks. On the contrary, when choosing a large block size, it will be less precise, but fewer bits will be needed for the prediction, and the computation time will be shorter [7] [8].

On the other hand, the HEVC standard is an evolution of H.264/AVC, and presents two new features that are key to improving upon the performance of its predecessor. In [14] an exhaustive analysis and study of intra coding in HEVC is carried out.

The first new feature is the image partitioning into encoding units called CTUs (Coding Tree Units), instead of using the traditional MB. Images are divided into blocks that can be up to a maximum size of 64x64 pixels and iteratively reduced by partitioning into four half-size sub-blocks. The minimum size of the blocks is 8x8 pixels. A CTU is a set of CUs (Coding Units) that define the image's subpartition in square regions of variable size. In addition, each CU can have one or more PUs (Prediction Units) and TUs (Transform Units), and can be partitioned into PUs. A PU is the elementary unit of prediction, and is defined after the last partitioned level of a CU, while a TU is a unit in which the transform and quantization are carried out. Unlike CUs, PUs can reach a minimum size of 4x4 pixels and a maximum of 64x64 pixels. They also have a tree structure and TUs range in size from 32x32 to 4x4 pixels. The relationship between TUs and PUs is that each PU can contain one or more TUs, and several PUs can be contained within a single TU.

All the CUs, as well as all the PUs and TUs, have a symmetrical form, whose dimensions are powers of 2. In other words, if the size of the upper level is $2N \times 2N$, the size of the next lower level is $N \times N$, and so on.

The other novelty is the intra directional prediction scheme known as angular intra prediction, which increases the number of predictors compared to H.264/AVC, reaching a total of 35, including 33 directional and 2 non-directional modes (DC and Planar). The set of all directional modes cover the spatial gradients in an arc of π radians. The increase in the number of directional modes allows a better prediction in the blocks that present a given spatial gradient [15]. Despite the increase in the number of predictors, the same H.264/AVC strategy is used as previously described regarding the use of neighboring pixels as a reference to make the prediction.

The x265 encoder, by default, does scan all angular modes, but in faster modes it scans only every fifth angular mode, and then, taking the best angular mode, it scans the neighboring angular modes at a distance of two [16]. The nvv4l2h265enc encoder, on the other hand, does not offer a parameter to skip certain angular

modes [9]. The x265 “medium” preset was selected in order to not use fast scan strategies in any of the evaluated encoders.

Finally, AV1 is entirely independent of the H.264/AVC and HEVC standards, due to it is not an evolution of any of them nor is it developed by the same organizations (ITU-R and ISO/IEC). However, the mechanisms on which the intra prediction is based are very similar with respect to those of H.264/AVC and HEVC, with some differences.

The first of the differences to highlight is in the block partitioning. In AV1 the maximum size of the blocks is 128x128 pixels (such blocks being known as superblocks), and they can include rectangular partitions. Figure 1 shows all 10 available partition modes, where the square blocks and rectangular blocks cannot be further subdivided. The subdivision indicated with an “R” is performed recursively in the same way as for partitioning the CTUs in HEVC. In contrast, the rest of the subdivisions are exclusive to AV1 intra prediction.

Regarding the prediction modes, AV1 supports 2 non-directional modes (DC and PAETH) and 8 directional modes corresponding to angles between $\frac{\pi}{4}$ and $\frac{23\pi}{20}$ radians. To those original 8 directional modes, another 48 additional modes are added, and these vary from each other by $\frac{\pi}{60}$ radians. In short, AV1 has 56 intra prediction modes.

Figure 1. AV1 block partition modes.

Finally, it should be mentioned that it also has 3 non-directional smooth predictors that perform block prediction using quadratic interpolation in vertical, horizontal, or average directions, with these predictors being called SMOOTH_V, SMOOTH_H, and SMOOTH, respectively [13]. These can be applied to blocks of all sizes. SMOOTH_V uses linear interpolation to predict blocks from the last pixel in the left column and the first pixel in the top row, while SMOOTH_H

performs an analogous process using the first pixel on the left edge and the last pixel on the top edge. SMOOTH consists of an arithmetic average of samples from the blocks predicted by SMOOTH_V and SMOOTH_H.

In addition, each residual block obtained in the prediction stage is transformed using a size that varies from 4x4 to 64x64 pixels.

IV. EMBEDDED SYSTEMS USED IN THE ANALYSIS

As indicated above, two embedded systems have been used to carry out this study and analysis, and the video encoders described in Section II will be tested on these devices. This section explains the hardware and software characteristics of both systems.

A. Raspberry Pi 4 board

Specifically, the version used is Raspberry Pi 4 Model B, with 4 GB of Random Access Memory (RAM), which was released in June 2019 by the Raspberry Pi Foundation. Raspberry is an embedded device consisting of a motherboard with computer functions that is endowed with a high level of external connectivity for educational use, and it can be purchased at an affordable price.

In terms of hardware features, it is noteworthy that it has 4 GB of RAM, as indicated by the version's name. The CPU is a Broadcom BCM2711B0 (64-bit quad-core Cortex-A72) that works with a clock frequency of 1.5 GHz and offers 2 to 3 times better processing performance than its predecessor, the Raspberry Pi 3, with a computing power of up to 9.7 gigaflops.

Another novelty with respect to its predecessor is that it includes 2 USB 3.0 ports, and is able to perform real-time hardware decoding of 4K and HD video formats at 60 frames per second (fps) with HEVC and H.264/AVC, respectively. Furthermore, it is possible to hardware encode HD sequences at 30 fps with H.264/AVC. However, it is not capable of hardware encoding 4K video. Power is supplied through a USB-C port requiring 5 V and 3 A, reaching a total power of 15 W.

With regards to the storage space, it is necessary to incorporate an external SD card to store the sequences to be encoded/decoded and the operating system. In this case, there is a *SanDisk Extreme Pro*, which is a 64 GB microSDXC storage card with a read rate of up to 170MB/s and a write rate of up to 90MB/s in order to avoid bottle necks in the coding process.

Concerning Raspberry 4 software, Raspberry has Raspbian as its operating system, which consists of an open-source distribution and free Linux software based on Debian.

B. Jetson Nano board

The multinational Nvidia announced Jetson Nano in March 2019 at the Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) Technology Conference. Their bid to compete in the embedded systems market offers a small module and excellent computing power at an economical price. The device is intended to perform artificial intelligence tasks, for example, image recognition, instant translation, and video encoding/decoding.

The Jetson Nano has hardware characteristics that are typical of medium-performance computers. Jetson Nano has a quad-core ARM Cortex-A57 MPCore as its main processor, delivering up to 472 gigaflops of power. It incorporates a GPU of the Nvidia Maxwell architecture with 128 Nvidia Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) cores. According to Nvidia, Jetson Nano is capable of encoding 4K videos at 30fps in HEVC. In addition, it has 4 GB RAM and 4 USB 3.0 ports. It also consumes only between 5 and 10 W.

Like the Raspberry Pi 4, Jetson Nano needs an external memory card for storage. In this study, the same card is used as for the Raspberry Pi 4.

Regarding the operating system, it is a modified version of Ubuntu 18.04 with all NVIDIA drivers pre-installed, which is offered by Nvidia on their website. The system is also compatible with other Linux systems if the proper drivers are installed.

To end this section, Table 2 presents a theoretical comparison of each device's video encoding/decoding performance, according to the manufacturer of each of the devices analyzed.

Table 2. Comparison of hardware encoding and decoding performance of Raspberry Pi 4 and Jetson Nano.

	Raspberry Pi 4	Jetson Nano
Encoding	HD 30 fps (H.264/AVC)	4K 30 fps, 9x 720p 30 fps. (H.264/AVC and HEVC)
Decoding	4K 60 fps (HEVC), HD 30 fps (H.264/AVC)	4K 60 fps, 2x 4K 30fps, 8x 1080p 30 fps, 18x 720p 30 fps (H.264/AVC and HEVC)

V. ENERGY CONSUMPTION

One of this paper's main goals is to show the energy consumption of the encoders on each of the two embedded systems. As mentioned in the abstract, this parameter is of utmost importance in any application where the energy supply is limited [17]. This section describes how energy consumption measurements have been carried out and the device used to perform these measurements.

As mentioned in previous sections, the devices on which video coding testing has been carried out are the Raspberry Pi 4 and Nvidia Jetson Nano embedded systems. Both systems are powered through a 5V micro-USB connector, which supplies up to 3A and 2A, respectively. Given that the Jetson Nano needs more power, it can be supplied with up to 4A at 5V through the barrel jack connector and even 5A through the expansion header. The board was powered through the jack connector during the simulations carried out.

For the measurements, the Fluke 8846A precision multimeter was used. The voltmeter and ammeter functions were used simultaneously, wiring the multimeter in such a way that the negative probe was shared by the two instruments. Figure 2 illustrates the supply and measurement circuit of the Raspberry Pi and the Jetson Nano.

After connecting all the precision multimeter instruments, a private Ethernet network was used to connect the multimeter to a local computer that logged incoming measurements. This allowed switching between the voltmeter and ammeter functions in order to measure both parameters at the same time.

Figure 2. Supply circuit of the embedded systems with voltage and current measurement.

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

With the aim of making a fair analysis of all the encoders under study, 22 video sequences with an 8-bit bit depth and created by the JCT-VC workgroup were used. This set comprises sequences that span a wide range of resolutions, with the highest being Ultra-HD (class A), and the lowest 416x240 (class D). The lower resolution ones are cropped from the UHD source footage [18]. Furthermore, it is important for the sequences to provide a wide variety of spatiotemporal complexity. The sequences are divided into 6 classes, with the first 5 classes having a natural source, and the last one (class F) having synthesized content captured from desktops and videogames. The resolution of the sequences in each class is as follows:

- Class A: (2500x1600).
- Class B: (1920x1080).
- Class C: (832x480).
- Class D: (416x240).
- Class E: (1280x 720).
- Class F: this class is not homogeneous with regards to spatial resolution (832x480, 1024x768, and 1280x720).

During the video encoding on both embedded systems, data for consumption and temperature were gathered.

A. Setup

Each sequence was encoded using 6 different Quantization Parameter (QP) values to obtain a wide Rate-Distortion (RD) range. The QP values used for H.264/AVC and HEVC were 22, 27, 32, 37, 42 and 47 [18].

However, the QP values were different for the AV1 standard implementation proposal (rav1e),

since the range of this parameter is different in this case, taking values from 0 to 255. To make a fair analysis between H.264/AVC, HEVC, and AV1, a QP value approximation was carried out for the rav1e encoder so that it would cover a similar range to the rest of the encoders. Thus, the QP parameter values chosen for the rav1e encoder in this paper were 75, 100, 125, 150, 175 and 200.

In the case of omxh264enc, it may happen that six encodings per sequence are not performed because the maximum bitrate of Raspberry hardware encoding is constrained to 20Mb/s. Furthermore, it is not allowed to enter the QP as an input parameter. Consequently, instead of varying the QP, the target bitrate was fixed as an input parameter, using the resulting bitrate from nvv4l2h264enc for each test sequence.

Next, Table 3 shows an example command line for each of the 3 software encoders used. In this case, Traffic sequence with QP 22 has been used as an example. The same parameters have been configured in the 3 command lines: information related to the sequence (resolution and framerate), QP and intra prediction.

Besides, the 3 encoders have a command that can activate acceleration techniques in encoding. In x264 and x265 the command is "--preset", while in rav1e it is "--speed". These commands optimize the trade-off between computing time and compression efficiency using speed-up encoding techniques. In the case of x264 and x265, the "medium" preset has been used, which is the default mode and does not activate acceleration techniques in intra prediction. In rav1e the default value (6) has also been used.

In conclusion, the comparison is considered fair since all the command line parameters have been configured in the same way and intra coding acceleration techniques have not been activated.

Table 3. Command lines of software encoders

Encoder	Command line
x264	<code>./x264 --demuxer lavf --input-csp yuv420p --profile main --fps 30 --input-res 2560x1600 --psnr -b 0 -I 1 -q 22 --psy-rd 0 --ipratio 1 --no-psy -v -o Traffic 22.h264 Traffic.yuv 2>Traffic 22.txt</code>
x265	<code>ffmpeg -s 2560x1600 -y -r 30 -i Traffic.yuv -c:v libx265 -profile:v main-intra -psnr -x265-params qp=22:psy-rd=0:ipratio=1 Traffic_22.hevc 2>Traffic 22.txt</code>
rav1e	<code>./rav1e Traffic.y4m --psnr --quantizer 75 --keyint 1 --verbose -o Traffic 22.ivf 2>Traffic 22.txt</code>

B. Compression efficiency results (bitrate vs. PSNR)

The parameters analyzed in this section are the encoded video bitrate together with its objective

quality, measured with the Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) metric. An encoder is regarded as more efficient the lower the bitrate is, and the larger the PSNR, and its performance is judged

using the well-known RD curves. The curve of the encoder that displays the best performance will be above that of the others.

Figure 3 shows the performance results for the Traffic sequence, which belongs to class A. It can be observed that *rav1e* presents the best performance in terms of quality/bitrate, followed by *x265* and *nvv4l2h264enc*. The encoders that offer the worst performance are those of the H.264/AVC standard. With regards to *omxh264enc*, it does not appear in the graph because the Raspberry Pi cannot encode sequences having the resolution that Traffic does by hardware. However, the same should not be the case for all sequences.

Figure 3. RD curves for Traffic sequence.

In addition, Table 4 shows the Bjøntegaard Delta rate metric (BD-rate), defined by ITU in [19], of the encoders with respect to *rav1e*. It was decided to use *rav1e* as a reference because it is the one with the best performance in most sequences.

The BD-rate indicates the average difference between RD curves measured as a percentage of the bit rate that is necessary to increase or decrease to achieve the same PSNR quality in both curves. A positive BD-rate means that the encoded bitrate using the encoder being compared is greater than the bitrate obtained with *rav1e*, and is therefore referred to as the penalty in bitrate terms [20] [21].

For each encoder, the sequences were encoded 4 times with different QP values (22, 27, 32 and 37). When calculating the BD-rate for *omxh264enc*, QP values of 32, 37, 42 and 47 were used for both encoders.

It can be observed that in the overall sequence set, *rav1e* presents the best performance, followed by *x265*. It is important to note that the hardware encoders do not offer better performance in terms

of quality/bitrate than the three software encoders analyzed.

Of the hardware encoders for the Jetson Nano, overall *nvv4l2h264enc* performed better than *nvv4l2h265enc*. However, for classes whose sequences are of HD resolution or higher (A, B and E), *nvv4l2h265enc* achieves better results.

With regards to *nvv4l2h265enc*, it fails to outperform the HEVC software encoder (*x265*) in any class. On the other hand, in average terms, *nvv4l2h264enc* obtains similar results to *x264*, and it even improves upon it in classes A, C and E.

The results obtained for *omxh264enc* can only be compared with *rav1e*, since different QPs from those applied with the other encoders were used. Cells containing Not Applicable (N/A) are due to the technical limitations of the Raspberry Pi, and the average result of the *omxh264enc* is misleading since the BD-rate cannot be calculated for classes A and B.

The only sequence that *rav1e* does not achieve the best performance for is *SlideEditing*, being surpassed by *x265*, *x264* and *nvv4l2h264enc*.

C. Computing time results

The second parameter addressed in this work is the efficiency of the encoder quantified as computing time. Table 5 displays each encoder's average computing time for the Raspberry Pi 4 system, and the Jetson Nano.

The computing time, which is measured in fps and shown in Table 5, was calculated as an average of the 6 encodings carried out for each sequence using the six QP values. The last row shows the average computing time for all the 22 sequences for each encoder on each embedded system, and the second column indicates the minimum computation time that must be reached to encode the sequence in real-time.

Columns 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 show the computing time of the software encoders. As expected, the sequences with the highest resolution (class A and class B) have the highest computing time, due to the larger number of bits to be processed. Similarly, those with the lowest resolution (class D) showed lower computing times; that is, they were encoded faster.

Table 4. Coding efficiency (BD-rate) results with respect to rav1e

Class	Sequence	BD-rate (%)				
		x264	x265	omxh264enc	nvv4l2h264enc	nvv4l2h265enc
A	Traffic	72.8	22.8	N/A	69.3	55.6
	PeopleOnStreet	108	46.3	N/A	107.2	96.3
B	BasketballDrive	275.9	170	N/A	291.1	275.8
	BQTerrace	129.1	70.1	N/A	145.7	147
	Cactus	114.8	65.7	N/A	121.1	93.7
	Kimono	185.2	70.4	N/A	175.6	112.1
	ParkScene	87.2	50.1	N/A	89.4	80.7
C	BasketballDrill	105.3	43.9	94.4	57.1	112.2
	BQMall	87.7	441	71	88.2	108.2
	PartyScene	47.7	309	59.7	54.4	74
	RaceHorses	64.4	276	136.4	67.8	66.7
D	BasketballPass	72.2	27.6	N/A	71.9	81.4
	BQSquare	47.4	30	63.1	58.1	88.5
	BlowingBubbles	44.9	25.8	43.4	49.9	66.8
	RaceHorses	54.3	20.4	84	57.6	47.2
E	FourPeople	122.4	53.4	34.2	115.9	117.1
	Johnny	216.9	94.3	116.2	214.7	169.4
	KristenAndSara	134.7	53.4	43.1	130.6	126.7
F	BasketballDrillText	73.1	27.3	111.7	79.6	99
	ChinaSpeed	51.5	24.7	55.3	65	131.5
	SlideEditing	-12.4	-21	N/A	-1	70.3
	SlideShow	65.8	13.9	87.8	101.7	162.8
	Average	97.7	45.1	76.9	100.5	108.3

Even though rav1e obtained the highest quality performance, it is unfeasible for real-time applications because its computing time is very high, being more than 100 times slower than required for HD sequences. On x264, it is not possible to encode 4K and HD sequences in real-time on the Raspberry Pi 4 or the Jetson Nano, but it is possible to work in real time with lower resolution sequences. However, x265 cannot encode any type of stream in real time.

Furthermore, it can be observed that the encoders compress faster on the Jetson Nano, regardless of the encoder being analyzed.

The last three columns show the computing time in frames per second of the three hardware encoders of the three hardware encoders, namely omxh264enc (omxh264), nvv4l2h264enc (nvv264) and nvv4l2h265enc (nvv265). It should be mentioned that, in the omxh264 results, the first two sets of rows are filled with N/A, because the Raspberry Pi was not able to encode those sequences by means of hardware, due to their high resolution.

It can be observed that the hardware encoders which ran on the Jetson Nano encoded the sequences at a higher speed than the H.264/AVC encoder did on the Raspberry Pi. With this data, we can say that the Raspberry Pi allows the streaming of videos of lower resolutions than HD in real time. Also, the Raspberry Pi's hardware

encoder shows an irregular encoding speed since the encoding time varies considerably. In the case of the Jetson Nano, real-time encoding of the HD and 4K streams is possible with both the encoders analyzed.

D. Energy measurement results

In the first phase, both voltage and current were measured for each embedded system. The 5V voltage source supplied a real tension of $5.173 \pm 0.016V$ to account for the voltage drop across the USB power cable. The current absorbed by each device was also measured.

The current across both the Raspberry Pi and the Jetson Nano embedded devices displayed a cyclical pattern with an average of 500 mA, and a recurring consumption increment of approximately 70 mA, as shown in Figure 4, where the average current consumed by the Raspberry Pi while idle has been plotted. This pattern of peaks and valleys does not appear in either of the embedded devices when they enter sleep mode. Raspberry Pi and the Jetson Nano perform essential background tasks required by the operating system, which explains this pattern. The current absorbed while encoding behaves in the same way, with the mean current absorbed being larger, as it consumes more resources when encoding.

Table 5. Average computing time of the software and hardware encoders.

Sequence	Software						Hardware		
	fps	Raspberry Pi		Jetson Nano			omxh264	nvv264	nvv265
		x264	rav1e	x264	x265	rav1e			
Traffic	30	8.78	0.03	9.98	0.28	0.05	N/A	78.5	81.66
PeopleOnStreet	30	8.51	0.02	9.35	0.28	0.05	N/A	79.37	81.67
BasketballDrive	50	16.41	0.05	20.54	0.59	0.1	N/A	95.17	97.77
BQTerrace	60	12.66	0.05	16.83	0.54	0.09	N/A	92.21	96.16
Cactus	50	15.84	0.05	17.76	0.54	0.1	N/A	96.62	96.7
Kimono	24	20.66	0.07	23.29	0.59	0.15	N/A	96.53	94.75
ParkScene	24	16.34	0.06	18.46	0.55	0.11	N/A	91.97	94.51
BasketballDrill	50	68.52	0.19	90.09	2.75	0.37	108.52	329.54	313.07
BQMall	60	78.1	0.22	92.02	2.79	0.45	101.51	330.77	322.18
PartyScene	50	53.93	0.19	68.34	2.34	0.37	47.6	332	325.44
RaceHorses	30	75.05	0.23	83.14	2.67	0.45	140.39	330.52	327.45
BasketballPass	50	299.6	0.91	337.53	10.97	1.75	437.47	808.24	762.01
BQSquare	60	226.25	0.89	259.87	9.68	1.64	379.85	788.24	769.74
BlowingBubbles	50	221.68	0.8	252.23	9.3	1.54	470.18	795.08	761.76
RaceHorses	30	270.9	0.91	269.89	10.33	1.63	573.65	793.94	807.25
FourPeople	60	45.16	0.12	45.46	1.34	0.23	38.94	211.01	206.76
Johnny	60	34.16	0.15	48.53	1.44	0.29	47.47	208.03	211.41
KristenAndSara	60	36.61	0.14	51.63	1.4	0.27	55.19	214.88	212.94
BasketballDrillText	50	66.78	0.19	85.84	2.7	0.34	83.52	331.28	328.39
ChinaSpeed	30	34.57	0.12	49	1.45	0.23	75.59	278.62	275.93
SlideEditing	30	29.56	0.08	35.67	1.19	0.14	23.15	204.77	203.21
SlideShow	20	56.65	0.17	67.55	1.66	0.32	58.86	212.67	198.82
Total		77.12	0.26	90	2.97	0.48	176.13	309.09	303.16

Power and energy consumption were calculated for each device using the voltage and current measurements. Figure 5 shows the average power absorbed while each encoding algorithm was running (in Watts), and Figure 6 shows the average energy consumed per frame while using each encoder, depending on the frame resolution in megapixels (MP). When encoding sequences with a frame size above 1MP using omxh264enc, the device runs out of memory or is unable to perform in real time due to the large frame size (class A & B).

Figure 4. Detail of the electric current consumed by the idle Raspberry Pi.

The power consumption of each algorithm was calculated by averaging the instantaneous power

consumed, which is equal to the current absorbed times the voltage across the terminals, and then those values were averaged as shown in (1). The energy consumption per file was calculated by numerically integrating the instantaneous power, which has previously been calculated, using the amount of time between measurements as timestep. This is represented by the summation shown in (2).

Figure 5. Power consumed by the devices according to the encoder and embedded system.

Figure 6. Energy consumed by the devices according to the encoder and embedded system.

$$P_{algorithm} = \frac{\sum_1^{N_{measurements}} V_i I_i}{N_{measurements}} \quad (1)$$

$$E_{file} = \sum_{i=t_{initial}}^{t_{final}} V_i I_i \Delta t \quad (2)$$

As can be seen from the results, a significant difference exists between the encoders with regards to their energy consumption, although all the encoders' power consumption is within the same order of magnitude, with the hardware-based encoders and the Raspberry Pi board being more efficient. However, each encoder's energy consumption is vastly unequal, with *rav1e*, both on the Raspberry Pi and Jetson Nano, consuming up to 1000x the energy used by the hardware-based Jetson Nano encoders *nvv412h264enc* and *nvv412h265enc* to encode the same frame. The encoding speed of each encoder accounts for this discrepancy. It can be inferred from both Table 5 and Figure 5 that both the energy consumed and the encoding speed of each encoder are directly proportional to each sequence's resolution.

E. System temperature results

Temperature measurements were carried out on both the Raspberry Pi and the Jetson Nano while

encoding. The temperature curves of these devices follow an asymptotic increase until stabilizing at a final temperature, at which they remain until the end of the encoding. Table 6 shows the final temperature of the Raspberry Pi and the Jetson Nano for each encoder. For the latter, the internal GPU temperature was also measured. The data for this table was obtained with the internal sensors of the embedded devices, scrapping the data reported by the programs *vcgencmd* and *tegrastats*.

The temperature measurements are displayed in Figure 7, and show the temperature of the Raspberry Pi and the Jetson Nano at the beginning of the encoding. As might be expected, there was a rapid temperature increase leading to the stationary state when the thermal energy dissipated by the heatsink became equal to the thermal energy output of the processor. Upon reaching the stationary state, the temperature remains stable, experiencing small variations due to the ambient temperature. As an example, these oscillations can be seen in Figure 8, which shows the CPU temperature of the Raspberry Pi 4 while it was encoding with the *rav1e* encoder. The average temperature during the stationary state is also shown and was equal to 78.6 °C.

The temperature values reported by both devices exhibit random variations of 1-2 °C due to the inaccuracy of the internal temperature sensors [22]. Furthermore, both *vcgencmd* and *tegrastats* represent the temperature as a discrete number with a resolution of 1 and 0.5 °C, respectively. To better know the data trends and improve graph readability, the temperature data have been smoothed out using a moving average. The moving average for each instant is equal to the average measured values from a certain point in time, which in these graphs corresponds to 1 minute.

The temperature patterns obtained for the Jetson Nano device were like those of the Raspberry Pi. Neither encoder used the GPU, and its temperature remained between 3-5 °C lower than the temperature of the CPU. And, according to the data in Table 6, which compares the final temperature of each encoder and embedded system, the Jetson Nano has a greater dissipation capacity, with a difference of up to 20 °C with respect to the Raspberry Pi while encoding with *rav1e*.

Figure 7. The temperature measured on Raspberry Pi and Jetson Nano while encoding.

Figure 8. CPU temperature of Raspberry Pi while encoding with rav1e.

Table 6. Embedded system temperature (°C) at the end of the execution of the encoders

Encoder	RPI	J. Nano (CPU)	J. Nano (GPU)
x264	75.0	56.0	53.5
x265		60.5	55.0
rav1e	81.0	60.5	56.5
omxh264enc	57.0		
nvv4l2h264enc		46.0	43.5
nvv4l2h265enc		46.0	46.0

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

After completing the study and analysis of the different encoders' behavior and performance on both the embedded systems, it can be concluded that, in general, it is possible to encode 2500x1600

resolution sequences in real-time with Jetson Nano in an intra prediction scenario with nvv4l2h264enc and nvv4l2h265enc. However, the Raspberry Pi is only capable of encoding 832x480 sequences in real-time with omxh264enc and x264. Below, our different conclusions are presented in more detail.

First, rav1e, which is an AV1 software encoder, shows the best performance in terms of compression efficiency, despite its long execution time, which prevents it from being used in real-time applications. In general, the software encoders (x264 and x265) of both standards perform better in terms of quality/bitrate than the hardware encoders (nvv4l2h264enc and nvv4l2h265enc).

Second, by analyzing the encoders' computing time, it can be concluded that the Jetson Nano has a higher encoding speed than the Raspberry Pi 4 for all the encoders. Quantitatively, the Jetson Nano outperforms the Raspberry Pi by 75.49% with regards to software computing time and by 20.15% with regards to hardware computing time.

In addition, with the data available in this paper, we can conclude that real-time video transmission can be performed with both systems using hardware encoders, except for higher resolutions such as Full-HD. However, it cannot be done with either x265 or rav1e due to their low computing time compared with the sequence framerate. Only x264 allows encoding in real time using software encoding, but in a low-resolution format.

Thirdly, regarding the energy consumption of the embedded devices, it is shown that the most critical factor is the execution time of each encoder. Rav1e, being at least an order of magnitude slower than the rest of the encoders, consumes almost 10 times as much energy as the next encoder. Power consumption is lower for hardware-based encoders, and the Jetson Nano embedded system displays greater robustness and reliability in hardware encoding than the Raspberry Pi in terms of time, system temperature, and power consumption. In terms of thermal behavior, the Jetson Nano also performs better, as its thermal equilibrium temperature during encoding can be up to 20 °C lower.

For future work derived from this paper, one possible avenue is to extend the number of embedded systems to be tested, including, for example, the Versal Prime Series VMK180 Evaluation Kit platform from Xilinx and the Google Coral platform. Furthermore, a new video standard, known as Versatile Video Coding (VVC) [23], is currently under active

development. The aim of a future paper would be to compare this against HEVC and AV1, but not necessarily on an embedded system. Besides, it is intended to carry out a more extensive study with a inter scenario (Is and Ps frames), in which it is analyzed and evaluated the energy consumption in embedded systems.

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